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PREVALENCE OF HbSAg (HBV) INFECTION AMONG ADULT PATIENT ATTENDING GENERAL HOSPITAL TSAFE, ZAMFARA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Hepatitis B virus infection is among the leading public health burdens especially in developing countries. In high prevalence areas, the most common routes of HBV transmission are prenatal and horizontal transmission. Also, heterosexual practices, unprotected sex, infection, blood transfusion as well as sharing of sharp objects are among possible routes of transmission. Hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection accounts for about 1 million deaths worldwide annually. This study was to determine the seroprevalence, distribution of HBV, factors associated with infection and the rate of infection among adult patient coming from different geographical area associated with General Hospital Tsafe, Zamfara State- Nigeria. A cross-sectional clinic base study among the patients was conducted, employing sampling technique. Data on demographic, social, and behavioral indicators were collected using questionnaires and blood samples tested for HBV. The overall total of (116) blood samples were collected intravenously and were screened for HbSAg infection, Of the (116) samples, 70 (60.3%) were males, 46 (39.7 %) were females. Out of the 70 (60.3 %) males 17 (14.7%) had HbSAg infection and of the 46 females 8 (6.9 %) were infected with HbSAg infection ($P= 0.017$), The Overall prevalence of HbSAg infection was 21.6 % (25 of 116). Statistical analysis showed that there was a highly significant association ($P= 0.05$). According to the age range, the distribution of HbSAg infection showed highest prevalence among patients aged 26-30 (8, 6.9%), however the lowest infection was

detected among aged 31-35 (4, 3.4%) years. Based on the educational status of the patients, frequency of HbSAg infection was higher; this study has demonstrated an HbSAg prevalence rate of 21.6 %. Its therefore demonstrates the higher increase in HbSAg prevalence among adult patient attending general hospital Tsafe, as a result of absent of HB immunization. There is a gradual increase in the prevalence of hepatitis B surface antigen in our environment possibly due to the lack of awareness and HB immunization. There is the need for awareness campaign within Tsafe community to limit the spread of the disease and the importance of Vaccine. They should be educated on the need to adhere to treatment and adequate management of HbSAg infections. The prevalence level recorded is due to lack of enlighten campaign in health matters or awareness in the source of infection. as government is not paying much attention to the problem. This has aggravated the problem of hepatitis B virus and other related disease in the study area.

KEYWORDS: Hepatitis B virus, Prevalence, Tsafe, Zamfara, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Hepatitis B also known as Serum hepatitis is a disease of the liver cause by a double stranded DNA virus of the family Hepadna virus, which is reported to be the main aetiological factor in over 75% of chronic liver disease worldwide (Ryan and Ray, 2004). Hepatitis B virus (HBV) is resistant to inactivation by heat and is highly infectious. It is 50-100 times more infectious than HIV and 10 times more infectious than hepatitis (Lavanchy, 2004). The virus is detected in virtually all body fluid (i.e Blood, Saliva, Semen, Vaginal Secretion, Menstrual blood and to lesser extent in perspiration, breast milk, tears and urine) of infected individual (Lavanchy, 2004). Hepatitis B virus infection is among the leading public health burdens especially in developing countries (Sameul *et al.*, 2004). In high prevalence area, the most common routes of HBV transmission are prenatal and horizontal transmission (Gitling, 1997). Also, heterosexual practices, unprotected sex, infection, blood transfusion as well as sharing of sharp objects are among possible means of transmission (Harry *et al.*, 1994). An estimated 50% of the global population is infected with hepatitis B Virus infection, with more than 350 million people as chronic carriers and over 1 million deaths annually (WHO, 1998).

The prevalence of HBV varies significantly over the globe with low prevalence of 2% reported in developed countries, while developing countries have prevalence of about 8.0% (Luke, 1991). Sub-Saharan Africa is reported to be hepatitis B virus hyper-endemic with 8-20% prevalence and approximately 50 million people are chronic carriers (Dronsten *et al.*, 2004). Hepatitis B virus infection is a serious health challenge in Nigeria, with seventy five percent (75%) of the total population exposed to the infection at one time of their life, and an estimated 12% prevalence of chronic carriers (Alao *et al.*, 2009). Due to the infectious and asymptomatic nature of HBV infection, poor health care facilities and inadequate monitoring, HBV infection remains a major challenge (Okoye and Samba, 2006) and the prevalence of HBV infection is disproportional within the Nigeria population (Alao *et al.*, 2009).

METHODOLOGY

The study was cross sectional and clinic-based with the Ethical clearance obtained from the college Ethical Committee of GH Tsafe, Zamfara State before the commencement of the study. The Sample size was determined using the formula for cross sectional studies which was proposed by Lwanga and Lemeshaw (1991), Grad and Araoye (2006). The sample size was determined based on the estimated HbSAg prevalence of previous studies with an estimated 9.9 % prevalence of carriers (Alkali *et al.*, 2022). Based on a confidence

interval of 95%, a 5% acceptable margin of error and the need for a sample size large enough to enable analysis by age groups, a total of 116 of the patients were used. All the patients attended GH Tsafe and gave consent to participate before they were included in the study and those who did not give consent were excluded from the study. Written consent was obtained from the subjects prior to data and sample collection. Demographic data such as age, sex, and education were collected. This was done after obtaining a prior permission from the College management. A structured questionnaire was used for the collection of data. The information obtained include, sex, age and occupation and people are made aware of the study and its benefit through health education. Two milliliters (2ml) venous blood of each of the study participant was collected into a Vacutainer with Advanced Semi-separator gel (SST II), (Belliver Industrial Estate, Plymouth, PL6 7BP, United Kingdom) using standard method (CDC, 2017). This was mixed by turning it 5 times upside-down and coded with unique identifiers (known to the study investigators only). It was then centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 5 minutes to separate the serum from the whole blood (Vanhaecke *et al.*, 2016). The specimen was then dispensed in to a well labelled container and was stored at -20°C until use (Vanhaecke *et al.*, 2016). HBSag Strip was used to test the presence or absent of HbSAg in the patient serum.

RESULTS

The overall total of 116 patients who sought healthcare services from GH-Tsafe, were screened for HbSAg infection. Of the 116, 70 (60.3%) were males, and 46 (39.7 %) were females. Out of the 70 (60.3 %) males, 17 (14,7%) had HbSAg infection and of the 46 females, 8 (6.9 %) were infected with HbSAg infection (P= 0.02). Out of the 116 patients tested for AVT-naïve, 25 (21.6%) were positive for HbSAg infection. The Overall prevalence of HbSAg infection was 21.6 % (25 of 116). Out of this figure 21.6 % (25/116) were AVT-naïve while 0 % were AVT-experienced patients (Table 1). Statistical analysis showed that there was a highly significant association (P= 0.05).

The table 1 shows the hepatitis B virus infection based on age of adult patient attending General Hospital Tsafe, Tsafe Local Government, Zamfara State. The age group between 20-30 (6.9%) were the highest percentage followed by 20-25 (6.0%) as well as 36-40 (5.1%) and the lowest infective was detected among age group of 31-35 (3.4%).

Table 1 Distribution of table based on age group

Age	No of Sample Tested (%)	No of Positive (%)
	<u>HbSAg Detection</u>	
20-25	28 (24.1%)	7 (6.0%)
26-30	22 (19%)	8 (6.9%)
31-35	11 (9.5%)	4 (3.4%)
36-40	30 (25.9%)	6 (5.2%)
Total	91 (78.4%)	25 (21.6%)

Table 2 shows the hepatitis B virus infection based on gender in which the male patient have the highest percentage of 17 (14.7%) and females patient with the lowest percentage of 8 (6.9%).

Table 2: The table shows the prevalence of hepatitis B virus based on male and female gender

Age %	No of Sample Tested (%)	No of Positive (+ve)
MALE	70 (60.3%)	17 (14.7%)
FEMALE	46 (39.7%)	8 (6.9%)
Total	116 (100%)	25 (21.6%)

DISCUSSION

This study has demonstrated an HbSAg prevalence rate of 21.1 %. This is higher than that of the 6.6% recorded in Enugu, Nigeria. It therefore demonstrates the gradual increase in HbSAg prevalence in Tsafe environment as a result of absent of HB immunization. It is also higher than the 7.6% reported by Chukwuka *et al* in Nnewi and also higher than the 9.9% reported by Aliyu *et al* in Tsafe at the time as this study. Earlier studies have also documented lower prevalence of HBV in Northern Nigeria like Enugu 9.4% by Agbede, *et al.* (2007)

The highest prevalence of HbSAg positivity was found in those patients aged 26-30 years with HBsAg Positive 8 (6.9%). This may be because at this age most persons are very active and exploring their world. However, it differs with the observations by Jibrin and Alikor who found highest prevalence rate among children 11-15 years. This difference may be because of increase in some high-risk behaviors including unprotected sexual habits among persons of this age group.

This pattern also indicates the predominance of horizontal transmission of HBV infection in our environment.

A slightly higher prevalence of HbSAg was observed among the males. Though the prevalence rates observed in this study are higher, it is same with the finding in Enugu earlier, in Port Harcourt and in Borno who observed a higher prevalence among males (Akani *et al.*, 2005).

The social class of the parents in this study was not significantly associated with HbSAg positivity. This may be because of equal exposure to the risk factors of HBV among persons of different social classes. However, in this study it was observed that the higher the social class, the lower the number of positive to HBsAg. This could be because people in the lower socioeconomic class are more likely to indulge in activities that may promote infection with HBV such as alternative medicine, share sharp objects and toothbrushes. This is similar to the findings of Komasa, and Emechebe. In 2004, the universal HB immunization was commenced in Nigeria though it was incorporated into the National Programme of Immunization (NPI) in 1995.

However, exposure to repeated injections sometimes with contaminated therapeutic injection equipment, probably due to ignorance, parental preferences, or lack of awareness of infection control practices and resources for sterilization, are very common. Also although not statistically significant as risk factors, but as has been documented previously blood transfusion and scarification marks have odd

ratios of 1.5 and 3.2 respectively, making them potent risk factors. This is true of occult hepatitis B in which there is presence of HBV DNA in the liver in the absence or undetectable serum HBsAg and measurable or immeasurable serum HBV DNA. It had been noted that history of blood transfusion was a sufficient risk factor for chronic hepatitis B infection, a major etiologic factor for primary

hepatocellular carcinoma in Africa. Sharing of toothbrush among siblings/household members was found to be statistically significant while bite by playmates was not. The alkaline nature of the saliva may have been contributory in hindering transmission through bite. However, an intraoral trauma during brushing could be the source of transmission. Also the chance of transmitting the virus through this route is likely to be substantial given the fact that such sharing is likely to occur over prolonged periods. This finding is similar to that by Nwokediuko.

There is a gradual increase in the prevalence of hepatitis B surface antigen in Tsafe environment possibly due to the lack of awareness and HB immunization. The vaccine may also be 100% protective. Sharing of sharp object, spoons, needle, nail cutter and sharing of cloth and toothbrush was found to be a significantly, Its recommendations that the HbSAg sero-positive result should undergoes Liver Function Test especially in patients with liver failure to reduce unnecessary administering of drugs to individuals that do not require therapy and there is need to for awareness campaign to limit the spread of the disease. The importance of Vaccine and Antiviral therapy should be emphasized to all patients and should be educated on the need to adhere to treatment and adequate management of HbSAg infections and the Efficacy of drugs should be monitored periodically to those on treatment to regulate the emergence and spread of the drug resistance Virus particularly HbSAg infections. Future researches are recommended, including, In vitro analysis such as identification of different antigens that share similar epitope with HbSAg antigen that lead to the decrease in functionality of the liver.

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